

Applying a Natural Capital Approach to Biodiversity Sensitive Farming: key considerations for policy change

Policy recommendations

Establish systems to monitor and evaluate the impact of biodiversity-sensitive farming policies

The implementation of the Natural Asset Profiling (NAP) approach can generate important information on the health of the farm system and to monitor its performance. However, to measure impacts, a long-term commitment to implementing soil and other regeneration policies is required because changes in Natural Capital may only manifest after several years (Golosov and Belyaev, 2013; Ogieriakhi and Woodward, 2022). A corollary is that short term policies can be ineffective.

Integrate biodiversity considerations into land-use planning to preserve critical habitats

The NAP highlights the importance of landscape features and soil restoration practices in enhancing biodiversity and crop productivity. However, the current CAP lacks targeted interventions to support wild pollinators and offers only short-term measures to maintain biodiversity at landscape scale (Cuadros-Casanova et al., 2023). While the CAP aims to extend landscape features to cover up to 4% of farmland, other policies – such as the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and the European Green Deal – recommend a minimum of 10% (Cuadros-Casanova et al., 2023). Dedicating 10% of farmland to natural features may generate trade-offs between environmental benefits, opportunity costs and food security. These can be better managed by planning natural capital improvements across the landscape and allowing market forces to guide the level of intervention on individual farms according to the opportunity costs of farming.

Encourage collaboration between governments, NGOs, and the private sector

Showcasing the benefits of biodiversity-sensitive farming, such as the reliance of production systems on soil fertility and pollinators, can help decide whether and how to take actions within the FC and accelerate the uptake of measures at the landscape scale. Large scale initiatives are not fully incentivised by the CAP. Subsidies mainly operate on individual basis, are used to support the income of the individual farm and their environmental efficacy is often limited because not addressing environmental issues operating at a vaster scale. To address this, the CAP should include measures that promote cooperation between farmers and support community-led implementation of biodiversity-sensitive practices (Moersberger et al., 2023).

Reforming Agriculture for Biodiversity and Sustainability: A Landscape-Based Approach

Farming plays a vital role in meeting the growing global demand for food. However, this activity cannot be sustainably delivered without a substantial change of the current agronomic practices to which are often linked with excessive use of nutrients, loss of soil fertility and simplification of natural habitats. In addition, the demand for calories from wealthier nations is driving the outsourcing of food production to the Global South, increasing deforestation (Binner et al., 2025) and threats to biodiversity. In Europe, amendments made to the EU Common Agricultural Policy in the last 30 years have not succeeded in halting biodiversity loss (Heyl et al., 2021). This policy brief explores these challenges by examining the relationships between landscape features and biodiversity and the contribution of agroecological practices in food production through the implementation of the natural capital (NC) approach.

Approach and results

The concept of natural capital (NC) refers to the stock of natural resources—such as air, water, soil, habitats, and biodiversity—that underpin ecosystem services. In this context, NC was used to support environmental monitoring within *farmer clusters*: groups of farmers who voluntarily collaborate to achieve shared goals, often as part of a transition toward biodiversity-sensitive farming. The NC approach helps promote utility and efficiency in environmental management (Mace et al., 2015), by focusing on elements of nature that provide value to people. It identifies stocks of natural assets that provide an array of ecosystem services, underpinning our economy, and make human life possible (Bateman and Mace, 2020). A simplified version of this framework, illustrating the cascade from natural capital to ecosystem services and human benefits, is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic of the natural capital approach showing the cascade between natural capital, ecosystem services and values. These relationships are not expected to be linear. Adapted from Costanza et al. (2014).

A framework, the Natural Asset Profiling (NAP) approach, was developed to characterise and evaluate how farm systems depend on and impact NC assets (Martino et al., 2023). NAP enables farmers and other practitioners to monitor the effectiveness of biodiversity-sensitive farming practices and to identify drivers and limitations of successful outcomes. To implement the NAP, 24 indicators (Martino et al., 2023) were selected covering a range of environmental topics (Table 1).

Table 1. Set of topics, and sub-topics chosen for the selection of natural capital indicators.

Dimensions	Topics	Subtopics
Environmental	Atmosphere	Greenhouse gases emission
		Soil carbon sequestration
	Water	Water Use & Withdrawal
		Water Quality
	Land	Land use (habitat diversity)
		Land Degradation/soil erosion
	Biodiversity	Crop Diversity
		Species Diversity
	Other Materials & Energy	Material Use (fertilisers, pesticides)
		Energy Use

The implementation of the NAP: measures of impact

The NAP was tested at the Cranborne Chase farmer cluster (England), located in the Area of Outstanding Natural Beauty of the same name. The cluster is composed of 19 arable and arable-livestock farms, covering an area of 20,000 hectares. The farms showed a high dependency on fertiliser use - nearly 200 kg N/ha/year, compared to an EU average of 68 kg N/ha/year. Livestock density was also high, at **2 livestock units (LU) per hectare**, roughly **three times higher** than the average EU pasture system (0.7 LU/ha), though consistent with the values found in improved grazing systems. In contrast, energy use was lower than the EU average mixed farming system (Martino et al., 2025). In terms of environmental impacts, biodiversity, particularly pollinators, is considered a critical aspect. The Biodiversity Shannon index for pollinators (0.7) was half the lower bound of the benchmark expected in natural areas, reflecting the limited presence and diversity of landscape features (Figure 2).

	impacts of crop production - CO2 emissions	average	Std dev	benchmark	Reference/note
	GHGs emissions from farming - tCO2e/t produce/year	0.21	0.08	0.2-0.3	A benchmark for the CO2e emissions per ton of cereal is 300-400kg per ton of product. This figure includes the CO2 emitted by fertilisers manufacturing AHDB and CHA (2022). Benchmark for only field operation 0.2-0.3
	crop diversity - Shannon Index	0.44	0.21	0.8	Typical values are generally between 1.5 and 3.5 in most ecological studies, and the index is rarely greater than 4. Applied to crop diversification, this indicator range from 0.8 to 0.9, where the highest value is achieved in case of organic farming (Schaak et al., 2023).
	pollinators diversity Shannon Index	0.71	0.13	1.5-3.5	Typical values are generally between 1.5 and 3.5 in most ecological studies, and the index is rarely greater than 4. The Shannon index increases as both the richness and the evenness of the community increase.
	Birds diversity Shannon Index	1.25	0.22	1.5-3.5	Typical values are generally between 1.5 and 3.5 in most ecological studies, and the index is rarely greater than 4. The Shannon index increases as both the richness and the evenness of the community increase.
	hedgerows stock- %	0.80	0.40	4.5	Several taxa would benefit from an increase in hedgerow extent in the United Kingdom to around 8-13.8 km/km2. 10km of hedgerow (estimating a width of 4.75 m) per km squared is equal to 4.75% of land. Staley et al (2023).

Figure 2. Key indicators measuring negative impacts on the environment. The most critical are reported in red. They refer to the need to increase the extent of landscape features and to increase birds and pollinators diversity.

The effect of natural capital on biodiversity

Non-productive features, such as hedgerows, have a positive impact on pollinators. Figure 3 illustrates the relationship between the proportion of farmland allocated to hedgerows and pollinator diversity. According to the model, an increase of 1% in the area of land supporting hedgerows corresponds to a 0.07% increase in pollinator diversity, as measured by the Shannon index. To raise the pollinator diversity in Cranborne Chase from a Shannon index of 0.7 to 0.8, the model suggests that the current hedgerows area would need to increase by approximately 200%. This implies that at least 2.4% of the average area (nearly 12 ha, compared to the current 4 ha) would need to be reallocated from crop production to hedgerow establishment.

Figure 3. Relationship between pollinators biodiversity and area of hedgerows represented by observations (coloured dots) and expected values (red line). Both variables are expressed in natural logarithm.

The impact of natural capital on production

Soil regenerative practices – such as agroforestry, conservation tillage, and use of cover crops – positively influence crop production by reducing soil loss. Using a production function approach, the effect of total energy (including energy used to produce fertilisers, as a proxy for capital) and avoided soil erosion (as a proxy for natural capital) were tested as predictors of crop output (Martino et al., 2025). The model estimates that the average reduction in soil erosion (0.7 t/ha/year) provides a marginal crop benefit of £500/ha, with natural capital contributing to 28% of crop production (Figure 4). The downward sloping curve in Figure 4 can be seen as a demand for natural soil fertility. By describing marginal crop productivity as a function of avoided soil erosion, this curve shows that there is margin to increase productivity for the farms located to the left of the red line. These farms have not implemented sufficient measures to reduce soil erosion, while those already reducing soil erosion at least at 1 t/ha/year have not much margin to get further economic benefits.

Figure 4. Impact of avoided soil erosion (t soil/ha/year) on the marginal productivity of crop (£/ha) at the Cranborne Chase farmer cluster. Blue dots are data points (farms); the interpolation of these points (dotted line) shows the demand of avoided soil erosion. We note that several farms perform better than average (red vertical line) and mainly three farms (located at the left of the red line) can get important benefits expressed as crop productivity from introducing practices reducing soil erosion.

Implications

Ecological implications

Creating habitats, such as hedgerows (Figure 3), is essential for wildlife – including insect pollinators which contribute to the production of highly pollinator-dependent plants, such as horticulture crops, fruit trees, oilseed rape, and field beans (Martino et al., 2025; Hünicken et al., 2022; Shivanna, 2022). In addition, soil regenerative practices like agroforestry and conservation tillage can help to reduce soil erosion (Figure 4) and increase carbon sequestration in soils and vegetation, helping to mitigate climate change (Panagos et al., 2021, 2020, 2015; Rehman et al., 2023).

Economic implications

EU farming suffers from soil erosion that is estimated to cause the loss of 0.43% of crop production annually, equivalent to € 1.25 billion (€ 105/ha in 2015) (Panagos et al., 2018). The economic model proposed in Figure 4 can be used to calculate the benefits of investing in soil erosion reduction strategies and compare them with gains in crop productivity. In addition, avoiding soil erosion can induce saving in fertiliser use. Martino et al. (2025) found that in Cranborne Chase, improving soil retention from **0.7 to 1.2 tonnes per hectare per year** (Figure 4) – the highest performance observed – could reduce nitrogen fertiliser use by approximately **33 kg/ha**, resulting in input cost savings of around **£13,200 per farm** (based on 2022 prices).

Benefits of improving productivity per unit of land can be compensated by a reduction in revenue (reduced in total production) due to the expansion of natural features like hedgerows. For the area of interest, expanding hedgerows up to 10% of the agricultural land (40 ha), as suggested by the Biodiversity Strategy 2030 (Cuadros-Casanova et al., 2023), may generate revenue losses at the Cranborne Chase of nearly £ 20,000 per farm that can be compensated only by public economic incentive of £ 600/ha. Expanding landscape features in areas characterised by reduced productivity, operationalising income diversification through agri-tourism or participating to private carbon markets can be considered a valuable strategy to cover the expected production losses.

References / Further Reading

- Bateman, I., Mace, G., 2020. The natural capital framework for sustainable, efficient and equitable decision making. *Nature Sustainability* 3, 776–783.
- Binner, A.R., et al., 2025. Using the natural capital framework to integrate biodiversity into sustainable, efficient and equitable environmental-economic decision-making. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 380, 20230215. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2023.0215>.
- Costanza, R., et al., 2014. Changes in the global value of ecosystem services. *Global Environmental Change* 26, 152–158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2014.04.002>.
- Cuadros-Casanova, I., et al., 2023. Opportunities and challenges for Common Agricultural Policy reform to support the European Green Deal. *Conservation Biology* 37, e14052. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.14052>.
- Golosov, V., Belyaev, V., 2013. The history and assessment of effectiveness of soil erosion control measures deployed in Russia. *International Soil and Water Conservation Research* 1, 26–35. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-6339\(15\)30037-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-6339(15)30037-X).
- Heyl, K., et al., 2021. The Common Agricultural Policy beyond 2020: A critical review in light of global environmental goals. *Review of European, Comparative & International Environmental Law* 30, 95–106. <https://doi.org/10.1111/reel.12351>.
- Hünicken, P.L., et al., 2022. Evaluation of interactions between honeybees and alternative managed pollinators: A meta-analysis of their effect on crop productivity. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 340, 108156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2022.108156>.
- Mace, G.M., et al., 2015. Towards a risk register for natural capital. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 52, 641–653.
- Martino, S., et al., 2025. Report on the natural asset profiling (NAP) and the potential for regional impact forecasting for farmer cluster and biodiversity sensitive farming using the NAP (No. Deliverable D7.4 for the EU-H2020 funded project FRAMEwork under Grant Agreement Number 862731.). The James Hutton Institute.
- Martino, S., et al., 2023. A protocol for Natural Assets profiling and assessment of impacts and dependencies of farming systems on natural capital. (No. Deliverable 7.3 of the project H2020 Framework project-grant agreement No 862731.). The James Hutton Institute.
- Moersberger, H., et al., 2023. Biodiversity monitoring in Europe: user and policy needs. *Conservation Letters* e13038. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.07.12.548673>.
- Ogieriakhi, M.O., Woodward, R.T., 2022. Understanding why farmers adopt soil conservation tillage: A systematic review. *Soil Security* 9, 100077.
- Panagos, P., et al., 2021. Projections of soil loss by water erosion in Europe by 2050. *Environmental Science & Policy* 124, 380–392. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.07.012>.
- Panagos, P., et al., 2020. A Soil Erosion Indicator for Supporting Agricultural, Environmental and Climate Policies in the European Union. *Remote Sensing* 12, 1365. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12091365>.
- Panagos, P., et al., 2015. The new assessment of soil loss by water erosion in Europe. *Environmental Science & Policy* 54, 438–447. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.08.012>.
- Panagos, P., et al., 2018. Cost of agricultural productivity loss due to soil erosion in the European Union: From direct cost evaluation approaches to the use of macroeconomic models. *Land Degrad Dev* 29, 471–484. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.2879>.
- Rehman, S. ur, et al., 2023. Soil organic carbon sequestration and modeling under conservation tillage and cropping systems in a rainfed agriculture. *European Journal of Agronomy* 147, 126840. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2023.126840>.
- Shivanna, K.R., 2022. The Plight of Bees and Other Pollinators, and its Consequences on Crop Productivity. *Reson* 27, 785–799. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12045-022-1372-8>.

About this Policy Brief

Publisher(s): The James Hutton Institute

Author(s): Simone Martino, Claudio Petucco.

Contact: simone.martino@hutton.ac.uk

Permalink: <https://zenodo.org/uploads/17304889>

Project name: FRAMEwork: Farmer clusters for Realising Agrobiodiversity Management across Europe

Project website: www.framework-biodiversity.eu
© 2025

All information contained in this policy brief was produced by the authors to the best of their knowledge and checked by them and the editors with the utmost care. However, errors cannot be completely ruled out. Therefore, all information etc. comes without any obligation or guarantee of the authors or editors. Both therefore do not assume responsibility or liability for any possible factual inaccuracies or damage resulting from the application of recommendations.

Funding

This Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 862731.